

A macroscopic bilateral modeling approach for reflective and transmissive metasurfaces

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Abstract—This paper presents a macroscopic bilateral modeling approach for Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) capable of simulating various cases, including transmissive and bilaterally reradiating RIS. Building on recent work, the approach is based on a general power balance at the RIS surface according to a few parameters, that accounts for both desired and parasitic reradiation modes on both sides of the surface as well as diffuse scattering and dissipation. The surface effect is described using a spatial modulation coefficient that embodies the wavefront transformation of each reradiation mode, including phase and amplitude modulation. Here the model is proposed and combined with a Huygens-based field calculation method to test its effectiveness in a few applications cases found in the literature.

Index Terms—reconfigurable intelligent surfaces, macroscopic modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

In the recent years, there has been a growing interest in Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface (RIS) technology which enables the manipulation of the reradiated - anomalously reflected or transmitted - radio wave characteristics. Such capabilities give engineers degrees of freedom to tailor the propagation environment [1], [2]. RIS can be implemented by the means of metasurface technology, using electrically-small printed scattering elements on a dielectric substrate or as reflect-arrays and transmit-arrays made with proper antenna elements [3]. The reconfigurability of RIS can be ensured using active elements such as varactors or p-i-n diodes in each unit cell. While the majority of the existing contributions in the literature focus on the ability of RIS to manipulate the reflected wave only, there is a growing interest in exploring other functions of RIS for wireless system application. Transmissive RIS that can manipulate the transmitted wave may play a crucial role, for example in ensuring coverage when the radio link ends are situated on opposite sides of a wall [4]. A potential application of transmissive RIS involves coating windows to improve radio signal transmission for indoor coverage while maintaining light transparency, as demonstrated in [5]. Moreover, to fully exploit their full potential, RIS may need to simultaneously manipulate both the reflected and transmitted wave [6]. The design of the RIS depends on the operating wavelength, the substrate material, the incidence angle and wave polarization: depending on those parameters and on the chosen technology, RIS can exhibit different power-efficiencies [5]–[7]. Other limitations and non-idealities include the finite

size of a RIS, scattering generated by realization imperfections and phase discretization, parasitic modes, and restricted angles of operation. Most RISs are limited to phase modulation only. However, amplitude modulation and/or non-local effects can be used to improve performance and efficiency [8].

In order to account for those characteristics while keeping complexity and computation time low enough to allow multi-RIS, system-level simulation, simple and yet realistic macroscopic models for RISs are necessary. Recently, parametric models have been proposed in the literature that take into account the physical structure of RIS, aiming at including all the non-idealities. In [9] a first parametric Huygens-based model was introduced, based on a power balance at the RIS surface. The power balance is based on the power conservation principle between the incident and reradiated waves according to a few macroscopic parameters that depend on the type of RIS and its technology. To account for the phase and amplitude modulation realized by the RIS, a so called spatial modulation coefficient was introduced. Furthermore, a ray-based reradiation model was developed in [10]. However, the mentioned models are conceived to model reflective RISs only. In the present work, we extend the foregoing power-balance approach to the bilateral case, therefore including also the application to transmissive and bilateral RIS, and we carry out a realistic model parametrization with respect to the existing RIS prototypes presented in the literature. Furthermore, we provide a few model application examples.

II. POWER BALANCE: BILATERAL EXTENSION

Here, we extend the model proposed in [9] by considering a general-purpose RIS that can reradiate the incident wave into both half-spaces. Merging the approaches proposed in [9] and [11], we reorganize and extend the model also to transmission, i.e. to the forward half space. The foundation of the model is a power balance defined for the local surface element: while it is local, to take into account non-uniform RIS realizations and non-plane wave illumination, that imply different incidence angles and different behaviour at different positions, non-local effects at the wavelength scale can be taken into account through the amplitude factor of the spatial modulation coefficient that is applied at a later stage. Thus, the power balance in [9] at the generic surface element dS takes the following form:

$$P_i = P_R + P_S + P_m + P_d + P_T \quad (1)$$

where P_R is the specularly reflected power, P_S is the total diffuse scattered power (due to mechanical or electrical inaccuracies), P_m is the total reradiated power in the anomalous directions, P_d is the power dissipated due to material losses and P_T is the transmitted power through the RIS in the "forward" direction, i.e. the same as incidence direction, but in the transmission half-space.

Since the model needs to consider a general case of a RIS that is designed to both anomalously transmit and reflect the incident wave, we express total diffuse scattered power as:

$$P_S = P_{S_R} + P_{S_T} \quad (2)$$

where P_{S_R} and P_{S_T} are the diffuse scattered powers in reflection and transmission respectively. The same holds for

$$P_m = P_{m_R} + P_{m_T} \quad (3)$$

where P_{m_R} and P_{m_T} are the anomalously reradiated powers in the backward (reflection) and forward (transmission) half-space, respectively. To characterize the power balance at the generic RIS surface element, we introduce the reradiation coefficients m_R and m_T that determine the fraction of incident power that is reflected and transmitted into anomalous modes. It is worth mentioning that in the case of periodic or locally periodic structures, the coefficients m_R and m_T can represent the power amplitude of Floquet modes. The symbol τ indicates the power transmission coefficient (or transmittance) that accounts for attenuation that transmitted wave undergoes when propagating through the RIS in the forward direction. Similarly, ρ is the power reflection coefficient (or reflectance) that accounts for reradiation in the specular direction. Under these assumptions and similarly to eq. (2) in [9], the power balance in (1) can be rewritten as follows, by expressing all its terms as a function of the incident power P_i

$$P_i = R_R^2 \rho P_i + S_R^2 (m_R + \rho) P_i + R_R^2 m_R P_i + R_T^2 \tau P_i + S_T^2 (m_T + \tau) P_i + R_T^2 m_T P_i + \alpha P_i \quad (4)$$

In (4), dissipated power P_d is also expressed as a function of incident power by using the dissipation parameter α , which accounts for the percentage of the dissipated power. In the above equation we see that a reduction factor R^2 is applied to both specular, forward, and anomalous reradiation modes. Moreover, differently from the definition of S^2 in [9], the diffuse scattering coefficient S^2 is redefined in this work as the ratio between total diffused power in the reflection (transmission) half-space and total reradiated power in the reflection (transmission) half-space, therefore as:

$$S_R^2 = \frac{P_{S_R}}{P_R + P_{m_R}} \quad \text{and} \quad S_T^2 = \frac{P_{S_T}}{P_T + P_{m_T}}. \quad (5)$$

For both the diffuse scattering coefficient S and the reduction factor R , subscripts "R" and "T" are used to distinguish between the reflection (backward) and the transmission (forward) half-space, respectively.

If we assume a perfectly smooth RIS and without physical or electrical imperfections, there would be no scattered power

($S_R = S_T = 0$) and the reduction factors R_R and R_T would become equal to 1: then in this case (4) would reduce to:

$$1 = \rho + m_R + \tau + m_T + \alpha \quad (6)$$

Here, ρ , m_R , τ , m_T and α are parameters that range from 0 to 1. Furthermore, as previously discussed in [9], this set of parameters may depend on the angle of incidence of the illuminating wave, which changes along the RIS surface for near-field illumination. Therefore, the power balance in (4) and (6) holds only locally. However, for far-field illumination this power balance can be applied globally to the whole RIS. Combining (4) and (6), the following relations between S and R are obtained:

$$S_R^2 + R_R^2 = 1, \quad (7)$$

$$S_T^2 + R_T^2 = 1. \quad (8)$$

Equation (7) shows that the higher the diffused power in reflection, the lower the reradiated power. The same holds true for the forward half-space as seen by (8).

As known from electromagnetic theory, in non ideal conditions, RIS can generate multiple parasitic reradiation modes (e.g. Floquet's modes of periodic structures). Let us assume that in general RIS anomalously reflects N propagation modes and anomalously transmits K propagating modes. In order to account for multiple propagation modes, we denote with m_{R_n} the reflected power coefficient of the n^{th} propagation mode and with m_{T_k} the retransmitted power coefficient of the k^{th} propagation mode. Then eq. (4) can be extended to the case of multiple reradiation modes as:

$$1 = R_R^2 \rho + S_R^2 \left(\sum_{n=1}^N m_{R_n} + \rho \right) + R_R^2 \sum_{n=1}^N m_{R_n} + R_T^2 \tau + S_T^2 \left(\sum_{k=1}^K m_{T_k} + \tau \right) + R_T^2 \sum_{k=1}^K m_{T_k} + \alpha \quad (9)$$

where $\sum_{n=1}^N m_{R_n}$ and $\sum_{k=1}^K m_{T_k}$ represent total (anomalous) power reradiation in the backward and forward half-space, respectively. The summations above do not include the indices $n = 0$ and $k = 0$ that usually refer to the specular and forward propagating modes, already taken into account through the coefficients ρ and τ . The power balance described in this section ensures that each reradiation mechanism is properly taken into account in the perspective of a macroscopic but physically-sound modelling of a RIS. It is worth noting that macroscopic parameters described above can be defined by measurements on prototypes or computed using electromagnetic simulation. As a last step, the radiation parameters m_{R_n} and m_{T_k} that satisfy power balance (9) and the proper spatial modulation functions for each reradiation mode are used to compute the reradiated field through the "antenna-array-like" (AAL) Huygens-based approach, described in previous work that corresponds to modeling the metasurface as a two-dimensional antenna-array: the metasurface is discretized into surface elements, then each element is modeled as an aperture antenna

that receives the incident power P_i and reradiates a spherical wavelet of power P_m according to a Huygens source radiation pattern while satisfying basic electromagnetic consistency requirements [9]. All the wavelets generated by all surface elements add up coherently to generate the overall reradiated wavefront. The field contribution of the generic element of the RIS with coordinates (x, y) at the observation point P is:

$$\Delta E_m(P|x, y) = \sqrt{\frac{m 60 P_t G_t}{r_i r_m}} A(x, y) e^{j \chi_m(x, y)} \frac{3 \lambda}{16 \pi} \frac{1}{(1 + \cos \theta_i)(1 + \cos \theta_m)} e^{-j k(r_i + r_m)} \quad (10)$$

where $A(x, y)$ and $e^{j \chi_m(x, y)}$ are the amplitude and the phase profile that RIS imposes on the reradiated field, r_i and r_m are the distance from the Tx to the RIS element and from the RIS element to the Rx, respectively, θ_i is the incidence angle and θ_m is the radiation angle toward the observation point P , whereas P_t and G_t are the transmit power and antenna gain. The overall reradiated field is obtained through summation of the reradiated field by each RIS element. More details can be found in [9].

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section some simulation results, obtained by applying macroscopic parameters of RIS prototypes found in the literature in the previous section, are presented. We consider two benchmark scenarios: one involving a transmissive RIS conceived for anomalous reradiation in the forward half-space which also reradiated a parasitic specular reflection in the backward half-space, and a focalizing RIS (meta-lens) that concentrates the incident power into a focus in the forward half-space. For the first case study, a non ideal, 5×5 m RIS placed in the xy plane and illuminated with an incidence angle of 20° by a plane wave linearly polarized along the y axis is considered. The operation frequency is 26.5 GHz, the incident field intensity is 1 V/m and the desired reradiation angle is 60° , which is implemented using a constant phase-gradient spatial modulation profile as shown in [9]. In this case, $m_T=0.746$, $\alpha=0.104$ $\rho=0.15$ (values are taken from prototypes in [4] [7]). As depicted in fig. 1, a portion of the incident power is steered toward the desired reradiation angle while another portion goes toward specular reflection. Additionally, a part of incident power is dissipated in the substrate. This simulation result highlights the potential of the model to reproduce a realistic RIS behaviour.

For the second case study, we consider a double-focalizing, bilateral lens that is able to focus a normally incident wave with 1 V/m intensity in two spots located in both the backward and the forward half-spaces, although here we only show the latter. RIS dimensions remain the same as in the previously discussed case except from the operating frequency that is 14 GHz, while parameters are $m_T=0.246$, $m_R=0.2785$, $\alpha=0.4755$ and the desired focus point at $(0; 0; -3\text{m})$ as in [6]. Focusing is implemented using a focalizing, circular symmetry spatial modulation profile as shown in [9], section IV.2. It is worth noting that the electric field intensity at the focus point is 9

Fig. 1: Non ideal transmissive case with $m_T=0.746$, $\alpha=0.103$

Fig. 2: Non ideal forward focus with $m_T=0.246$, $\alpha=0.4755$

times higher than the incident field intensity as shown in fig. 2, where the field on a xz plane orthogonal to the RIS passing through the focus is shown. The size of the focal area is similar to the wavelength, in accordance with lens theory.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have presented a macroscopic bilateral modeling approach for RIS, extending previous work to incorporate both reflective and transmissive functionalities. By applying a power balance at each RIS element, our extended model accurately predicts RIS behavior. We have demonstrated the effectiveness of our approach through simulation results in two benchmark scenarios: a transmissive RIS and a double-focalizing bilateral RIS. Future work includes refining the model with non-linear effects, alongside experimental validation. Overall, our approach offers a simple yet powerful tool for optimizing RIS-based wireless communication systems, promising advancements in various applications.

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